

Roles of Social Studies in Curbing Kidnapping and Enhancing Socio-Economic Development of Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the roles of social studies in curbing kidnapping and enhancing socio-economic development of Nigeria. The study reviewed the concept of Social Studies, global origin of kidnapping, origin of kidnapping in Nigeria, role of Social Studies in curbing kidnapping in Nigeria, and role of Social Studies in promoting socio-economic development of Nigeria. Kidnapping entails unlawful carting away of a person or persons by violence against his or her will, with the ultimate goal of achieving a specific goal including financial, political, social or religious benefits. To say that kidnapping is damaging to Nigeria's national security is to state the obvious. It has affected the socio-economic development of the country as socio-economic development can only be attained via peace and tranquillity. The study concluded that there is need for the Nigerian Government to come up with Social Studies curriculum contents that could challenge the causes of kidnappings.

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Introduction

Social studies describe the dealings of human being with his total environment whether it is physical, socio-political, religious, or economic features of the human environment. The modern society is encountering a lot of problems in the aspect of socio-economic wellbeing of the citizens. No nation can accomplish the sustainable development goals devoid of socio-economic development. Social and economic prosperity is needed if any nation is to prosper.

Socio-economic development can be described as the process of social and economic change in a society. Socio economic development clasps changes happening in the social sphere especially of an economic nature. Socio-economic development is measured with indicators, such as GDP, life expectancy, literacy and levels of employment. Alterations in less-tangible factors like personal dignity, freedom of association, personal safety and freedom from fear of physical harm, and the extent of participation in civil society are also taken into consideration (Nwanegbo & Odigbo, 2013).

The socio-economic structures of the nation have been declared deficient on several occasions as a very porous economic make-up (Raheeb, 2018). Excessive oil dependence, negligence of agriculture and an inadequate use of scientific method in goods and services production have aggravated these problems. Reasons for this judgment are dependent on evidences from stratification, poverty and inequality that have culminated at a very high rate of corruption among working class people and crime like kidnapping, robbery, raping, terrorism, ritual killing and fraud rampant among the jobless youths recently. It is sad however to note that Nigeria being the largest economy in Africa is one of the top five countries in the world with large numbers of people living in poverty and crime such as kidnapping.

Concept of Social Studies

The development of Social Studies in Nigeria was targeted at ending colonial education content and replacing it with indigenous education content, which seeks to solve social problems of the society through the inculcation of social values and positive attitudes (Abdu-Raheem, 2013; Augustine, 2009). Social Studies is a means of instilling national consciousness, effective citizenship, national unity and rebuilding (Yusuf, 2017). The national aims of Nigeria therefore seek to realize the development of the person, society and the national economy which in a broader context concerns with socio-economic and political life of the society (Nwafor, 2014).

According to Oluwagbohunmi (2017) almost all in the society is expected to do what is right to one another. This is being just and fair in all things and showing regard for human rights. It also encompasses the vision of a society where there is equity. Therefore, Social Studies is a subject that is meant to groom learners into having socially acceptable behaviours. The acceptance of Social Studies as a subject in Africa was to make education more related to Societal needs (Oluwagbohunmi, 2013). Social Studies was introduced into countries including Nigeria in response to the societal needs and aspirations (Osalusi, 2009, 2010). Therefore, there is the demand for proper implementation of Social Studies programme in schools to embed citizenship, open mindedness and harmonious connection between the learners and their physical environment as early as possible (Oluwagbohunmi, 2012; Adanikin, 2017).

The aims of social studies cannot be over flogged. Philosophically, the introduction of social studies in Nigeria was to discover a systematic and holistic way of solving human

challenges. The subject social studies was also introduced as a corrective measure towards our already acquired educational system from our colonial masters who educated Nigerians for their political and economic interests (Kabir, 2014). The aims include:

- To build awareness and comprehension of our social and physical environment among our citizens in order to preserve and keep them for national development,
- To cultivate positive attitudes among Nigerian citizens towards the spirit of friendliness and collaboration needed for a healthy nation and to inculcate appropriate values of uprightness, integrity, hard work, fairness and justice.
- To develop appreciation for diverse nature and interdependence of Nigerian communities, national and international communities in the students.
- To cultivate the spirit of responsibility, respect for worth and dignity of individuals, production of effective citizenry, cultivation of values of democracy, patriotism, development of attitudes of tolerance and accommodation, increasing awareness of our physical and social environment for better human interaction and progress.
- To educate the child to get relevant body of knowledge and necessary information for personal development and to add to the betterment of mankind (Kabir, 2014).

Global Origin of Kidnapping

Kidnapping is a global phenomenon that poses a problem to people, but the rate at which a person to fall victim depends on the society, usually the nature of the social structures, moral strength of people and other factors in the environment. The researcher would apply some level of historicity to trace the root of kidnapping. The approach would be to identify the first case ever at the global level, in Africa, how and when the dysfunctional behaviour presented itself in Nigeria before it blow-out to Southwest like a wild fire at its zenith of destructive inflammation without an extinguisher nearby.

Kidnapping is an ancient social malady perhaps as old as man in structured societies. The Christian bible recorded the first case of kidnapping at the world level. Although, the bible did not give a specific case of a kidnap incidence, the Old Testament recorded that “anyone who kidnaps another and either sells him or still has him when he is caught must be put to death” (Exodus 21:16). From this narration in Exodus; a Book which comprise of diverse elements, emanating from various sources, ranging from the 8th until the 2nd century BC (Nwadiorah & Nkwocha, 2011), one observes that the act of abduction must have been a well-known occurrence in biblical era no wonder this legislation was made.

According to recent history, kidnapping re-emerged in 1874 when a four year old Charlie Ross from Philadelphia, U.S.A was kidnapped and a ransom of 20,000 US Dollars was requested (Ugwuoke, 2010) and Lindbergh case in 1932 (Allison, 2000). In the Lindbergh’s case, Lindbergh’s child was the centre of a conspiracy, parents’ suffering, and the challenges police encountered during enquiry process, were exacerbated by widespread speculation, fabrication and serial random notes (Alexander & Klein 2009). However, the early African societies were marked with the incidence of slave trade. In this manner, Ugwu (2010), proclaimed that the weak and the underprivileged were captured and sold into slavery.

As earlier manifested, the phenomenon of kidnapping took the form of child abduction for ransom (Ezeibe & Eze, 2016). Over the years, however, kidnapping has transformed into a refined organized crime, with a lot of political and economic undertone. Recent developments point to the fact that the crime has grown into a sort of franchise, with appreciable trappings of business-like exchange (Tzanelli, 2017).

The root of kidnapping in Africa will lead to unpleasant and wicked activity of slave trade and slavery ravaging the continent of Africa. The slave or triangular trade as it was popularly called, that started in the late 16th century was deepened in terror and abduction as a way of getting their victims. Umukoro (2010) affirms that “kidnapping is an unhappy repetition of the obnoxious slave trade when our helpless ancestors were taken by fellow blacks, via organized raids and orchestrated tribal warfare, and sold into white slavery”.

Origin of Kidnapping in Nigeria

Ugwulebo (2011) explained that in the colonial era, the colonialists came to some parts of the world, such as Africa, carried away their able bodied men and women and sold them to far away countries who required human labour for their plantation and other services. Ugwulebo (2011) had noted that gun powder, gin, rum and other materials were offered by the Europeans to the Africans in exchange for slaves shipped yearly from ports in Nigeria. Therefore, slavery and kidnapping were like two sides of a coin.

In the early traditional Nigeria society, human sacrifice prolonged kidnapping. Ugwuoke (2010) rightly declares that people were kidnapped for ritual or social reasons. The African traditional worshippers only believed in sacrificing to appease the gods. The sacrifice may surpass animal sacrifice, and the priest could be stimulated by the gods to order for human beings; to achieve this kind of sacrifice, the needed person could be kidnapped and killed in a sacrificial manner. Ugwuoke explained that kidnapping was majorly for the purpose of sacrifice either to appease the gods or for the burial of a prominent chief or warrior. Precisely, to conduct a successful burial of important citizen like chiefs and prominent warriors needed a human head. Hence, warriors engaged themselves in hunt of targets to be kidnapped.

Kidnapping and slave trade are two sides of a coin with the difference emanating from who the abducted persons are sold to. While the slave traders sold their victims to foreigner in often far countries, kidnapers sold theirs to their own people for discussed prices. The merging factor amidst all this is the dehumanization of victims that are reduced into mere object for exchange and as such causing a direct assault on human dignity (Umukoro, 2010).

Besides, Nwadiorah and Nkwocha (2011) discovered that the act of kidnapping amplified in Nigeria after the Nigerian civil war in 1970 which bare many youths with military experience to some misconduct. Nigeria has not been created at the time of slave trade, but the several people that comprise part of the geo-political enclave now referred to as Nigeria were completely involved in the sad experience as agents or victims of slavery. The social system of some large empires in Africa (Nwadiorah & Nkwocha, 2011), Nigeria inclusive, embraced slavery as part of property owned by wealthy and royal homes.

Kidnapping had been a part and parcel of the Nigerian society apart from the slave trade. Since the extra-judicial kidnapping and false incarceration by the subsequent military government are perfect indications of these certainties. In this regard all way of unlawful confinements and arrest that may not need ransom before release are still within the confines of kidnapping. Yet, kidnapping in Nigeria nowadays can be said to be an effect of the “Resentment against inhuman treatments and poverty in the Niger Delta of the country” (Ugwulebo, 2011). Kidnapping was unchecked in Port-Harcourt on February 18, 2006 by militants to make known their demands. It was a way of drawing local and international attention to the underdevelopment, environmental degradation and plight of the inhabitants of the area, no thanks to government inactivity and activities of oil companies (Ijediogor, 2010). Ijediogor observed that the basic objectives of the kidnapers of foreign oil workers

were identifiable because at the beginning ransom were hardly demanded and rarely paid since it was not geared towards economic gains but as a means to drive home their point on the struggle for the region.

This business venture and money making crime of kidnapping moved from Port-Harcourt and indeed South-South geopolitical zone to South-Western states. Ugwulebo (2011) captured this transfer of kidnapping from the South-South states when he affirmed that the South-Westerners got polluted, whether through the process of social osmosis occasioned by interaction and association. Ugwulebo further asserted that, the South-Westerners appear to have outsmarted their masters and are practising the vocation far more than their masters.

Kidnapping is on the increase in Nigeria. Statistically, Nigeria records above 1,000 kidnapping incidents a year, and there are many that are unreported (Catlin Group, 2012). The British government has criticized the fact that at least 25 British and dual British citizens and more than 200 other foreign citizens who have been kidnapped in the Niger Delta area since January 2007 alone. That is why Fage and Alabi (2017) affirmed that one of the elements of militancy and/or insurgency in the Niger Delta is kidnapping. From the unstable state in the Niger Delta, kidnapping has spread across the nation.

Kidnappings can either be for financial or political gain. Victims were originally foreign oil workers, but today many are local citizens, often staffs of international oil and oil service companies, and not necessarily rich and anyone whose family might pay a ransom can be targeted. In June 2012, police rescued Christian Obodo an international footballer, who was kidnapped in church (Catlin Group, 2012).

There exists a high threat of kidnapping and other armed attacks targeting oil and gas facilities and staffs. This is also applicable to ships and oil rigs at sea off the coast of the Niger Delta. In January 2012, kidnappers abducted a US citizen from his vehicle in the Delta and killed his security guard. In April 2012, criminals kidnapped a US national in Imo State and a Spanish citizen in Enugu State in separate incidence. In May 2012, an Italian national in Kwara State was kidnapped by criminals. A Lebanese national was also kidnapped in Kaduna State and his Lebanese colleague was killed during the abduction ruthlessly in same year. Two engineers – one British and one Italian – were murdered by their captors in March 2012 when Nigerian security forces, with help from Britain, tried to rescue them. They had been held hostage by Boko Haram (an Islamic fundamentalist group) for ten months (Catlin Group, 2012).

Kidnappings of western nationals for ransom have also been credited to Boko Haram. Georges Vandebeusch, a French Priest was also kidnapped in November 2013 as well as that of a seven-member French family, which is believed to have produced a ransom of USD 3 million which took place in Cameroon (Barna, 2014). It has also attacked schools and universities: the massacre of sleeping students in dormitories in February 2014 (Barna, 2014). On 14th April, 2014 the sect kidnapped 250 female students from Government Girl's Secondary School, Chibok, Borno State (Shuaibu, Salleh, & Shehu, 2015).

Another associated group, Ansaru, has also targeted Western nationals (kidnappings), Christians and the government. It is active in the northern states, primarily Kano, Katsina, Yobe, Bauchi and Borno. The existence of strategies similar to those of al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) has led some to advise that another potential leader of the organisation is Khalid al-Barnawi, who was a member of AQIM and trained in Algeria and might be the link

between the two organisations (Barna, 2014). In the Catlin Group's (2012) report, military-led rescue attempts can end in the deaths of hostages.

Kidnapping is not an emerging crime as some observers may want to hold (Caplan, 2015). It has been around as an essential criminal pathology of the contemporary society (Tzanelli, 2017). Existing scholarly thinking on the subject matter is nonetheless still evolving.

Role of Social Studies in Curbing Kidnapping in Nigeria

The introduction of social studies into the Nigerian national curriculum of schools as an helpful measure was designed to proffer solution to man's problems in a holistic form. As an interdisciplinary subject, it springs idea and knowledge that will assist in the study of man from other social sciences (Osalusi, 2014). As a tool for crime control, it tries to expose the child to the knowledge of his social and physical environment so as to appreciate and conserve it. It tries as much as possible to cultivate appropriate values and attitudes of effective citizenship among the students.

Social studies is an interdisciplinary subject that explores into other social sciences to extract ideas, thoughts, methods and generalizations in order to study and resolve the challenges of man in a wholistic way, has lots of roles to show in crime control in Nigeria. These roles of social studies in monitoring kidnapping are not farfetched. Looking back at the roles of social studies in Nigeria, one should be able to see vividly its roles in crime control (Gibson, 2017).

Through the awareness of our physical and communal environment, citizens are made to comprehend the evils linked with the act of kidnapping. The inculcation of suitable attitude, values and beliefs among our citizens has a big role to play in tackling crime among the youths. For instance, via the study of social studies, one is made to have feeling of concern towards some aspects of one's environment, love and concern for one another. It is believed that when positive attitudes, values, beliefs and love for one another are inculcated into the learners, they should not include themselves in anything that will overstep on another person's happiness. For instance, when one has feeling of concern his/her neighbour, one will do everything to protect his/her interests. One will not rob, kidnap, gossip, kill, lie, conspire, or even plot against him. If such person is in government, he will encourage and support him instead of seeking his downfall (Abubakar, 2013). This is why social studies is viewed as a curricular subject whose main concern is for the spreading and instilling the values and virtues linked with an effective entity in the minds of learners as prospective citizens (Abubakar, 2013).

Similarly, since social studies help to develop in the students' appreciation for the diverse nature and interdependence of Nigerian communities the knowledge of social studies will help us to understand that even in the mist of our diverse nature i.e. cultural, religious, ethnicity, class etcetera; we need each other to survive. When these are at the back of our minds, the issues of religious crises, political crises, ethnic conflicts and other vices will begin to die a natural death (Kabir, 2014).

In a similar vein, social studies teach the child to attain relevant body of knowledge and information important for his personal development. The knowledge of social studies eventually aids the child to have all it takes to be independent and responsible citizen who can fend for himself. This point out the issue of poverty, illiteracy, unemployment and greed which are main causes of crime in every society. These four challenges put together lead to: kidnapping, Robbery, killing, vandalization, cultism, drug trafficking, among others. But if one

has the right knowledge and fact needed to be self-reliant, live comfortable and participate fully in respect to the development of the society as social studies portrays, no one will be involved in any of the above listed criminal acts thereby decreasing the rate of crime in our society (Otse, 2017).

Since social studies is viewed as an avenue for the inculcation of values of democracy, patriotism, tolerance and accommodation for one another, it plays the role of tackling and controlling the crime in our society. Through the value of democracy, one becomes a responsible citizen, has right to vote and to be voted for, the need for free and fair election, needs for self-governing judiciary, need for independent electoral commission etc. The inculcation of the spirit of loyalty to the learners via the study of social studies equally is a strong means of controlling kidnapping in our society. Through the study of social studies, learners are made to have a sense of belonging, know their duties, rights as citizens. They should be able to aid and encourage as well as participate in the development of any good programme by the government and not disrupt its own government (Sofadekan, 2012). Social studies also assist in the development of tolerating and accommodating attitude among our learners. It exposes the students to appreciate unity in diversity. This further helps the students to tolerate and to accommodate one another.

Role of Social Studies in Promoting Socio-economic Development of Nigeria

Promotion of economic expansion and independence via the teaching of tolerance, togetherness, patriotism and unity in Social Studies Education in Nigeria raises national understanding, socio- economic development and retrieval as well as stability. Social Studies do stress the values of responsible and good living, accountability and diligence. However, in contemporary Nigeria, many are afflicted with the “get-rich-quick” syndrome and incorporated corruption wholeheartedly. Corruption is identified as the most devastating vice that is demanding the Nigerian economy and thus the abolition of corruption in the society via the teaching of Social Studies positive attitudes and values help to eradicate corrupt practices in society. Economic development can only be attained via peace and tranquillity, economic stability and hard work. Social vices affecting democracy, economic recovery, self-reliance and stability are identified as dishonesty, disloyalty and misuse of offices and public funds among others (Osalusi, 2014).

This makes Social Studies the most effective device for eliminating such vices and promoting the needed social, economic and democratic values in society so as to enable individuals and the society at large to alter their attitude towards social vices like corruption, violence and idleness to achieve economic recovery and stability. Introduction of social studies education into Nigerian school curriculum cannot be over emphasized. This is due to the fact that it infuses in the young a love of the country thereby fostering national unity which is essential to our development as a nation.

It contributes in achieving national goal by depending on its peculiar methodology using inquiry, topical, problematic, project activities and other approaches to expose the children to the pros and cons of various situation, so that they can attain at their own independent, conclusions based on reasoned judgment. Social studies education in Nigeria has a special duty to perform in transforming Nigeria into a modern state. They include soothing the social and political wounds of the past decades, nurturing the most recent hopes in good ethnic group link and nationalism, and the engendering constructive reforms to make the nation a fair and progressive society. It also helps to nurture the desire for self – reliance, national efficiency and national pride.

Moreover, social studies education adds in the attainment of national goals via citizenship education. Citizenship education refers to the culture of certain behaviours, knowledge outlooks and values which are created in the culture which the individual participate. A citizen however, is one who adapts to certain accepted practices, holds a particular belief that is honest to certain values, partakes in certain activities and conforms to norms which are often local in character.

The role of Social Studies in fostering economic recovery and steadiness can be seen in various endeavours. Social Studies Education in Nigeria shows the role of fostering the desire for independent, national sufficiency and national pride (Abubakar, 2013; Osalusi, 2014). Abubakar (2013) observed the aims of social studies education to decide their consistency with the goals and objectives of Mass Mobilization for Self-Reliance, Social Justice, and Economic Recovery (MAMSER), and found them to be steady in giving rise to independence in the society. Musawa (2016) pointed out that oil accounts for 80% of government revenue and 90% of Nigeria's export and cautioned the need to look beyond oil. Social Studies inculcate the value of self-reliance and national sufficiency which can lead to economic recovery and stability.

Social Studies Education supports hard work and self-employment among people in the society. Social Studies instil the values of hard work, self-reliance and employment through the inculcation of the right values and attitude towards agriculture and other vocations for self-employment and self-reliance. Osalusi (2014) argues that the teaching of social studies makes independence attainable in Nigeria. Honesty and hard work are core values inculcated on the younger generation in Nigeria. Honesty and hard work among citizens will eventually eliminate corrupt practices among Nigerians and instil economic recovery and stability.

Social Studies being the study of man in his social environment deal with the study of man's economic life as well. Concept of entrepreneurial education properly integrated into the Social Studies Education curriculum at the secondary and tertiary levels promotes self-employment and economic stability. This would establish job opportunities and eliminate high level of unemployment, poverty and crimes in the society (Mezieobi, Ogangwu, Ossai & Young, 2013). It would also increase the level of economic growth and development in the country (Abdu-Raheem, 2015; Orisa, 2012).

Poverty alleviation education via Social Studies in Nigeria is targeted at eliminating the high level of poverty in the country as Nigeria and other countries, by baring learners to the values of self-reliance, chastisement, honesty, hard-work, creativity and skills to improve the national economy. It is ill-fated to note that many people in Nigeria see public offices and funds as their route to wealth and that poverty is equivalent to honesty and doing the right thing. Ajala (2012) perceived that many politicians know that they play dirty but appear to concede to it and give impression to the youth that it is a profitable venture and seemed to also think that their situations were conferred on them with the sincere justification to use contracts as sources of revenue for themselves and their political parties.

Osalusi (2014) perceived that a man can be a complete failure in life despite his other successes if he is deficient of good character and qualities such as honesty, patriotism, humility and hard work, which are important to true success in life. Therefore, the role of Social Studies in economic recovery and stability in Nigeria is making positive contributions towards independence as Social Studies is able to correct these inequities in peoples' insights. Kabir (2014) explained the increasing social problems among teenagers in Nigeria as a

manifestation of joblessness, which has generated nonstop violence across the nation. In acquiescence, Kabir (2014) also declares that the level of deficiency in Nigeria is responsible for the violence among teenagers as joblessness, inadequate housing, poor physical and social infrastructures succeed. The love for huge and quick acquisition of wealth, regardless of the source, has made the youth indolent and impolite. Ojie (2007) lamented that Nigeria is obviously one of the typical countries in the sub-Saharan Africa with the challenge of poverty reduction, alleviation and education. Social Studies, therefore, educate on the values of hard work, patience, honesty and perseverance. These values would help Nigerians to inculcate honest work, living and prosperity and adopt the right attitude towards work, wealth creation and poverty.

Social studies hire collaborative instruction and learning which entails relevant activities and instruction to inculcate skills and values to young students in society. Social Studies Education inculcates concepts on contemporary issues in Nigeria into the curriculum and imbibes these through Information and Communication Technology (ICT), which helps learners to obtain useful information for social living. Mezieobi and Tamuno (2017) described contemporary issues as sensitive upcoming issues in the Nigerian society that needs national attention, such as increasing poverty, prostitution, kidnapping, political violence, herdsmen violent fights with farmers across the state of Nigeria, amongst others. Such vocations as ICT skills, agrarian practices, home economics, simple business education skills and other relevant skills can be gained via vocational studies as portrayed by contemporary issues in Social Studies Education. These vocational objectives in social Studies Education are educational values that would familiarise students and citizens with social skills and national awareness to improve the quality of life in their territories (Mezieobi & Tamuno, 2017). These would assist to revamp the economy via self-employment in terms of Nigeria's GDP and income *per capita* as well as raising standard of living nationally.

Social Studies Education instils values to the students and citizens in order to develop effective citizenship. Mezieobi, Ogaugwu, Ossai and Young (2013) proposed values integration in the Social Studies curriculum content at the tertiary level to alleviate against greed, corruption, leadership ineptitude, nepotism, god-fatherism, and other evils that have debased Nigeria's moral integrity and democratic existence as an honourable nation. Orisa (2012) also planned the instillation of social values as what Nigeria needs to alter from her current corrupt and poverty propensities to life of purity and make a complete turn-around from materialism, moral decadence, false sense of value, tribal feud, religious intolerance, social injustice, economic sabotage to a new national re-orientation of excellence, merit, dignity and intrinsic worth of human life as the basis of Nigeria's value system. Social Studies curriculum should target constructing moral personality which demands many strategies and techniques in teaching methods, skills, and knowledge to build and sustain social values (Mezieobi, Ogaugwu, Ossai, & Young, 2013).

Socio-political values deal with peace, tolerance and non-violent co-existence amongst other values. The achievement of these values in Social Studies aids social and political stability which builds the enabling environment for economic recovery and stability in Nigeria. Socio-political values deal with honest democratic values, socio-economic and political stability, peaceful co-existence, tolerance, unity, togetherness, patriotism as well as nation building. Democracy cannot thrive the 21st century with extreme poverty and violence, which if not eradicated would hinder economic recovery and stability (Dogara, 2018).

Conclusion

Kidnapping is an ancient social malady perhaps as old as man in structured societies. Kidnapping entails unlawful carting away of a person or persons by violence against his or her will, with the ultimate goal of achieving a specific goal including financial, political, social or religious benefits. It is a crime which entails holding a person against his will thereby depriving his liberty and endangering him to the threat of murder or assassination and demanding a ransom before his release. To say that kidnapping is damaging to Nigeria's national security is to state the obvious. Kidnapping causes a veritable threat to Nigeria's sustainable development in the light of the following:

- i. it causes loss of life, a danger to public safety
- ii. it damages economic growth and development by way of capital and investment flight
- iii. It results in negative view about Nigeria on international scene, with its negative effects on trade, tourism and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)
- iv. it builds an atmosphere of public insecurity, thereby risking the prospects of societal progress
- v. it has often cause loss of investment capital, shutting down of businesses, and joblessness etc.

There is need for the Nigerian Government to come up with Social Studies curriculum contents that could challenge the causes of kidnappings. Teachers should let the learners be aware of various forms of kidnapping so that they can employ preventive measures not to fall victim of kidnapping.

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